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IMPORTANT ASPECTS OF ESTABLISHING A POC QUALITY SYSTEM OUTSIDE HOSPITALS, THE NOKLUS MODEL

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ABSTRACT

Point of care testing (POC) in primary health care (PHC) has other needs than laboratory testing in Hospitals.

In Norway, with a sparse population of 5.5 mill people, there are 2,3 physicians and 2,2 co-workers, on average, at a physician's office. In addition, laboratory work is carried out in e. g., nursing homes, home care, and oil platforms.

In 1992 it was decided that if laboratory work should be carried out in primary care, there should be an organization that should guarantee the quality of this work, and Noklus was established.

The organization should deal with the following questions:

- Which constituents shall be analyzed at the GP office, nursing homes, etc ?

- What POC instruments should be used in primary care ?

- How to secure analytically correct (enough) results ?

- How do perform correct interpretations of the results ?

- What tests should be requested in primary health care in the most common clinical situations ?

In 2021 NOKLUS had about 3600 participants of which about 1760 were from general GP offices (99,2 of all) and 950 nursing homes (95 % of all). All participation is voluntary. A total quality system has been developed and is described in **Stavelin, A., Sandberg, S.:** Harmonization activities of Noklus – a quality improvement organization for point-of-care laboratory examinations. *Clin. Chem. Lab. Med.*, 2018; 57: 106–114.